

Greener Journal of Business and Management Studies

ISSN: 2276-7827 Impact Factor 2012 (UJRI): 0.6670 ICV 2012: 6.03

Market Information Access Capability of Rural Farmer in Nga Son, Thanh Hoa, Viet Nam

By

**Le Van Cuong
Ngo Thi Thuan
Nguyen Hung Anh**

Research Article

Market Information Access Capability of Rural Farmer in Nga Son, Thanh Hoa, Viet Nam

Le Van Cuong^{1*}, Ngo Thi Thuan², Nguyen Hung Anh³

¹Science and Technology Administration Office, HongDuc University.

²Faculty of Economics and Rural Development, Hanoi University of Agriculture.

³Faculty of Accounting and Business Management, Hanoi University of Agriculture.

*Corresponding Author's Email: levancuong@hdu.edu.vn

ABSTRACT

This research analyzes the impact of farmers' capability to access market information on the improvement of farmer household livelihood. For this purpose, a fieldwork was conducted in Nga Son district with specific objectives: (i) To describe the market information system in Nga Son, Thanh Hoa; (ii) To identify the farmers' capability of access, understanding and use of market information; (iii) To explore the influence of access and use of market information on the change of farmer household economic condition; and (iv) To determine farmer's advantages and disadvantages of access to market information in Nga Son.

The results show that: (i) The system provides MI service has initially formed in Nga Son district, in which the extension station and staff play as key roles; (ii) The farmers' capability of access in the district still remain at average level and farmers are sluggish in access to market information service; (iii) The farmers' capability of access to market information closely related to their annual incomes; (iv) Factors that impact on the farmers' capability of access to market information including educational background, economic condition of household and effective supports and interventions of local government, of which the economic conditions of households is the main factor.

Based on empirical results mentioned, our proposed suggestions are: (i) Strengthen the market information system; (ii) Improve the capability to access market information of farmers through training courses; and (iii) Increase public awareness and investment within refurbishing the transportation systems, restructuring the marketing system, promoting the development of cooperatives, enhancing the application of high technologies such as Internet, mobile phone, radio and newspaper to provide reliable market information services.

Keywords: Market information, market information service, access to market information, farmers' capability, farmer household economics.

INTRODUCTION

Market information occurs in the processes of buying and selling of agricultural inputs, outputs and services (Tiago and Yen, 2007). Thus, agricultural market information includes demand and supply of agricultural commodities and involved input and service sectors. The term shall include all data transmitted via the market data interface and the reference data interface (SIX, 2012). To specify the aspects of market information, Shaun et al (2008) indicated that basic market information as commodity price data linked where possible with market demand conditions. The objectives of these information is to assist farmers and be able to monitor the market and make better decisions on where to sell their products and to negotiate for improved prices rather than being compliant price takers.

Concerning the market information service, Giovannucci et al (2001) and Andrew (1997, 2011) defined that market information service is the service operating by either public or private sectors. The service collects information involving prices and quantities of traded agricultural products from rural assembly markets and then disseminates information on a timely and regular basis by media to farmers, traders, government officials, policy makers and others including consumers. Another definition by AAACP (2011) stated that market information service is a special service by its function of gathering and sometimes analyzing different sources of market information then accommodating market participants. The objective of such services is to improve the understanding of the market operation and make the information more accurate, timely and transparent (AAACP, 2011). Tiago and Yen (2007) pointed out that farmer can have access to market information from several sources which are formal and informal. Accordingly, the formal sources are implemented by government agencies' staff such as extension stations, market

experts, newscasts and broadcasts, internets, newspapers, magazines etc... Informal sources are provided by individuals as other farmers, companies, agro-processors and non-government organizations.

In Vietnam, rural agricultural production has played important roles in the nationwide economy. It is indicated that there are 15.3 million households living in rural area, of which an approximate 10.36 million agricultural farm households contributed to 20 percent of the total annual GDP and provided jobs to two third of the total labor force (GSO, 2011). On this account, farm households are substantially considered as a main economic factor in rural areas, which ensures the sustainable development of the sector. However, there are lots of constraints that these farm households have encountered. Due to the prevailing problems of limited information and knowledge, rural farmers have struggled with labor productivities, market-price driven decisions, small-scale productions, inadequate capital investments and exploitation by other traders which in turn decline the hope of improving their main source of income. Therefore, the accessibility, the understanding and the usage toward market information are the key factors to enhance the efficiency of their production and marketing.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in Nga Son district of Thanh Hoa province. The sampling procedure was structured into two stages. First, three communes Nga My, Ba Dinh and Nga Tan were chosen due to their distinctive characteristics: (i) Nga My is located near markets with good transportation infrastructure; (ii) Ba Dinh, in the central part of the district, is located not so far from markets with average conditions for transferring and selling agro-products; (iii) Nga Tan is isolated and greatly distant to the markets. Second, a representative village of each commune with the total number of 30 households was randomly selected, classified and investigated according to household types (better-off, average and poor). The household selection process was done by the head of village.

Primary data was gathered in term of general farmer production and marketing conditions, farmers' awareness of market information and market information services, farmers' market access, farmer's complaints and suggestions toward market information services. The semi-structured questionnaires, the discussion with local authorities and farmer group, and the PRA tools are primary data collection method. Interviews contained a limited number of set, closed questions, designed to elicit basic quantitative data, and a range of open-ended questions guided by a checklist of discussion topics. Interviews were designed to uncover key aspects of farmer household production and marketing strategies, particularly with respect to integration into the market through their awareness, understanding and usage of various information sources. Members of investigated local authorities were the cooperatives, farmer unions, people committees, head of villages, extension staff...etc. Secondary data from statistical materials, research papers and government documents regarding household's income and expenditure and related government subsidy programs (from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, the General Statistics Office and the Extension Department of Nga Son) also were collected in this study.

The surveyed data was classified, described and compared in term of criteria of household types, household income and level of market access. Quantitative and qualitative data were encoded and organized in SPSS program. The analytical procedure was stratified into two stages: the calculation of WAI (Weight Average Index) and GINI index. The criterion which indicates the market information access levels are displayed in the Table 1 below.

Table 1. Criteria of market information access level

Access level	Categories		
	Awareness and Understanding	Skill and Method	Applicability
1. Very high (1 point)	Thoroughly understanding of MIS both in theory and reality	Proficient skills for MI access. Timely access (daily update).	Well applied in making decisions about production, buying inputs and selling outputs.
2. High (0.8 point)	Basically understanding of MIS both in theory and reality	Basically skills for MI access. Weekly update.	Can be applied for making decisions about production, buying inputs and selling outputs.
3. Average (0.6 point)	Partially understanding of MIS both in theory and reality	Having both skills and methods in access to MI. Weekly update.	Difficulty applying in making decision about production, buying inputs and selling outputs.
4. Low (0.4 point)	Little understanding of MIS both in theory and reality	Limited skills and access to MI. Monthly update.	Making decision about production when other had done.

5. Very low (0.2 point)	Unawareness of MIS both theory in and reality	Lack of both skill and access to MI. Not timely access (monthly update)	Unable to apply in making decision about production, buying inputs and selling outputs.
----------------------------	---	---	---

Source: Own elaboration

RESULTS

Market information system in Nga Son is organized, implemented and coordinated between many agencies and departments at all levels. All activities of this service are controlled by the people’s committees (Figure 1). These agencies and departments have close relationships with each other. They support each other in providing the farmers information regarding new technical procedures, weather forecast and diseases prevention, and especially the market information. In this system, extension plays the most important roles by creating the public market information services to maximize farmer’s benefits through identifying the most needed information regarding their production.

Fig 1. Nga Son market information system

The analysis of farmers' capability regarding market information access was based on three criteria. These includes their awareness and understanding about market information, skills and methods to access to market information, and their applications reflected the acquired market information (Tiago and Yen, 2007). This part focused on Weighted Average Index (WAI), as mentioned in the research methodology, proved that the farmers' capability to access to market information in Nga Son still remains at average level. All of which, the criteria awareness and understanding the market information 0.6 was the highest in general (Table 2). In addition, the criterion of applicability also reached 0.49 on the average. However, the skills and methods reach the lowest in all sub-criteria which is 0.44. The methods of contacting with MI service's staff and participating in training merely reach 0.23 and 0.36, respectively.

The value of WAI regarding access to market information was clearly higher in Nga My and Ba Dinh than in Nga Tan. For example, the average WAI of Nga My was the highest 0.55, while the Ba Dinh WAI reached 0.51 and Nga Tan WAI reached 0.46 only. The reason is because Nga My located is in the central part of the district where it is adjacent to the assembling market plus well-constructed transportation system. This commune's educational level and economic conditions are much better than in Ba Dinh and Nga Tan. Ba Dinh is quite far from the center yet it has more convenient transportation system. Regarding the advantage of having one assembling market and better economic conditions, Ba Dinh hence

achieved the higher rate of WAI than Nga Tan. Lastly, Nga Tan is remote away from the center of the district, which has poor transportation system and economic condition leading to insignificant agricultural productivity. These explain the lowest rate of WAI of this commune as indicated in the above.

In respect of WAI in different household groups, the farmers' ability regarding market information access in the better-off (WAI 0.63) was significantly higher than the others which are 0.51 of the average group and 0.38 of the poor group. Due to factor of economic condition, households of the poor and average groups often practice on small production scale, obsolete technical procedure, inadequate capital investment and neglected market information. Hence, their production not only did not meet the market demand resulting in unexpected returns yet also questioned their unstable livelihood. On the other hand, the better-off household group often practice on much larger scale with sufficient capital investment and updated technical procedure. Trigger their decisions with available market information has always brought them out of market risk that the other group has sometime suffered.

Table 2. WAI regarding farmer's market information access in Nga Son

Criterion	Commune			Economic condition			Total
	Nga My	Ba Dinh	Nga Tan	Better-off	Average	Poor	
Understanding and Awareness	0.64	0.54	0.61	0.71	0.61	0.49	0.60
Contents of MI	0.63	0.57	0.61	0.68	0.61	0.53	0.60
Nga Son MI system	0.66	0.53	0.63	0.74	0.62	0.47	0.61
Roles of MIS's agencies and staffs	0.65	0.53	0.58	0.71	0.59	0.46	0.58
Skills and Methods	0.49	0.47	0.37	0.54	0.45	0.34	0.44
MI sourcing	0.63	0.53	0.55	0.62	0.58	0.52	0.57
Contact with MIS's staffs	0.24	0.25	0.20	0.28	0.22	0.20	0.23
Training Participation	0.42	0.37	0.30	0.45	0.36	0.28	0.36
Frequent Update MI	0.67	0.71	0.44	0.79	0.66	0.38	0.61
Applicability	0.52	0.54	0.42	0.66	0.50	0.33	0.49
Production Planning	0.59	0.52	0.51	0.62	0.55	0.46	0.54
Inputs Allocating	0.49	0.50	0.39	0.68	0.47	0.24	0.46
Sales and Marketing	0.49	0.59	0.37	0.68	0.48	0.30	0.48
Average	0.55	0.51	0.46	0.63	0.51	0.38	0.50

Source: Household survey, 2012

The criteria showing the understanding capability of market information was highest in comparison with other criteria in the same categories, for example these criteria reached 0.60 on the overall district while the skills and methods and applicability only achieved 0.44 and 0.49 respectively. The reason of this empirical fact comes from two aspects, which are firstly the education levels of farmers and secondly the effective media market information program at the local. On the contrary, the criteria of skills and methods were lowest in all categories. Apparently, these criteria of Nga Tan was merely 0.37 and 0.34 accounting for poor group while the criteria of understanding and applicability of these two reached 0.42 and 0.33 respectively. The cause of this problem rooted not only from the poor accessibility of farmers but also by the weakness and inadequacy in both quantity and quality of MI services in the district. This is assumed as persistent and ongoing problem sets of Nga Son market information system and related participants.

Market information access capability of Nga Son farmers reflects different income level (Table 3). As mentioned, the procedure of synthesizing and comparing the WAI presents the different results of average annual income and Gini index.

Table 3. Influence of MI access capability on farmer's income

Categories	Communes			Economics conditions			Total
	Nga My	Ba Dinh	Nga Tan	Better -off	Average	Poor	
WAI	0.55	0.51	0.46	0.63	0.51	0.38	0.50
Income	88.32	80.46	57.98	129.97	66.56	37.73	75.59
Gini index	0.30	0.28	0.35	0.16	0.29	0.37	0.32

Source: Household survey, 2012

Among the three investigated communes, the relation between the farmer's capability to access market information and farmer household's income was significantly evidenced in Nga Tan. The fact is the poorer the MI access capability of farmer the lower income level they achieve. Apparently, these indicated in the 0.46 WAI and 0.35 Gini index leading to the lowest household's average income of 57.98 mil VND of Nga Tan. On the other hand, these

criterion in Nga My and Ba Dinh speak the opposite fact, which show the higher WAI of 0.55 and 0.51 as well as the lower Gini index of 0.3 and 0.28 in corresponding to higher income level of 88.32 and 80.46 mil VND respectively. In three different economic condition groups, the better-off and average earned 129.97 and 66.56 mil VND in their annual income, which explains the WAI respectively 0.63 and 0.51, and the Gini index 0.16 and 0.29 in turn. Meanwhile, with lower value of WAI 0.38 and of Gini index 0.37, the poor group only achieved 37.73 mil VND income annually.

In order to improve the development of household livelihood and rural economics in Nga Son district, appropriate solutions and specific strategies for improving the farmers' capability for market information access are absolutely necessary. To do so, this paper research's purpose is to clarify the dimension of market access in terms of understanding the advantages and disadvantages in farmers' capability to access market information within their decision making processes (Table 4). There were up to 72.22 percent of households who claimed that they found it easy to obtain market information from other farmers by cell phone or direct communication. Most of them believed in this source of information. Approximately 54.44 percent of households said that there were many media programs providing market information and about 43.33 percent of households asserted that they had favorable rural infrastructure conditions to reach the market. However, the quality of information from these sources was often limited as mentioned above.

Beside the advantages, the farmers in Nga Son had encountered many disadvantages that inversely influenced their capability to access reliable sources of market information. There were up to 78.89 percent of household which claimed that they always in lack of official market information from government agencies and MI services. In addition, there were around 40.00 percent of households that perceived the inadequate local authority supports and interventions in agricultural market management. As a result, there were about 72.22 percent of households which complained that both inputs and outputs markets in rural areas were completely dominated and exploited by middleman and other traders.

Table 4. Advantages and disadvantage of Nga Son farmer to access MI

Categories	Commune			Economic condition			Total
	Nga My	Ba Dinh	Nga Tan	Better-off	Average	Poor	
Advantages							
Abundant MI on medias	76.67	63.33	23.33	76.92	65.71	20.69	54.44
MI sharing between farmers	63.33	83.33	70.00	73.08	68.57	75.86	72.22
Good rural infrastructure	96.67	10.00	23.33	65.38	40.00	27.59	43.33
Others	0.00	0.00	23.33	0.00	5.71	17.24	7.78
Disadvantages							
Difficult MI sourcing	73.33	86.67	76.67	84.62	71.43	82.76	78.89
GOV intervention and support	53.33	36.67	30.00	61.54	34.29	27.59	40.00
Dependency	80.00	50.00	86.67	65.38	77.14	72.41	72.22
Others	6.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.86	3.45	2.22
Farmer recommendation							
Government control and manage	40.00	83.33	83.33	80.77	60.00	68.97	68.89
Consolidate MIS and MI service	76.67	76.67	70.00	84.62	74.29	65.52	74.44
Others	3.33	3.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.90	2.22

Source: Household survey, 2012

According to farmer's suggestion to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of market information system in Nga Son, around 68.89 percent of households suggested that the state and government agencies should strengthen their roles in managing both agricultural input and output markets. Also, 74.44 percent of households desired to participate and consolidate MI services in order to assist and consult farmers in production planning and production mechanizing as well as efficient inputs sourcing and in-time sale of their products.

CONCLUSION

There is widespread controversy that smallholder farmers require improved accessibility to agricultural market information to raise their farm productivity and living standards. The prevailing narratives on farmer's market information access in rural Nga Son are characterized by two major features.

First, smallholder farmers are seen as their production and marketing operated under dismal market information access conditions with generally high levels of remoteness, insignificant infrastructural changes and inadequate local government supports and concerns. These associated high marketing costs and risks and stagnant farmer's willingness to access supporting services. Moreover, the private sector recently has not been greatly motivated to crowd out the state roles in agriculture after the inception of market liberalization.

A second feature is a lack of specificity about what is meant exactly by market information access. Assertions of "good" or "poor" market information are ubiquitous, but how is "good market information access" defined? Concerning inaccurate, blurred and delayed market information, small farmers in remote areas face higher input costs, lower output prices and fewer buyers competing for their surplus production, which together result in disincentives to adopt new technologies and produce for the market. These reinforcing market access problems contribute to stagnant productivity growth and mire millions of rural farm households in chronic poverty.

The analysis demonstrated the most important aspect of farmer's market information access in Nga Son, which is in order to address the appropriate proposed recommendations to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of interventions and changes in the system. In brief, it could be implied that these obtained facts pointed out that most farmers in Nga Son were very interested and relied on the necessity of accurate, transparent and timely market information. This once again loudly states the interrelation between the market access capability and outcomes in return for farmers in Nga Son.

REFERENCE

- All ACP Agriculture Commodities Programme (2011). Market information services, Pacific Brief, No.1 August 2011.
- Andrew W. Sepherd (1997). Market information services, Theory and Practice. FAO Agricultural Services Bulletin 125, Rome 1997.
- Andrew W. Sepherd (2011). Marketing Extension Guide 2, Understanding and using market information. Market Linkages and Value Chain Group Rural Infrastructure and Agro-Industries Division, FAO, Rome 2011.
- Giovannucci, Daniele, Sepherd and Andrew (2001). Market information service, Munich Personal RePEc Archive (MPRA), 2001. Online at [http://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/17193/MPRA Paper No. 17193](http://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/17193/MPRA_Paper_No._17193), posted 08. September 2009.
- GSO (2011), Preliminary results of the rural, agriculture and fisheries census in 2011 SIX SWISS EXCHANGE (2012), Directive 6: Market information, Effective from 01/01/2012.
- Shaun Freris, Patrick Engoru and Elly Kaganzi (2008), Making market information service work better for the poor in Uganda. CAPRI working paper No.77. May 2008.
- Tiago and Yen (2007), Guide to Agricultural Marketing Extension with special reference to Vietnam, Module 1 *Improving access to market information and understanding of marketing opportunities.*
- Tiago and Yen (2007). Guide to Agricultural Marketing Extension with special reference to Vietnam, Module 2, *Improving access to market information and understanding of marketing opportunities.*